

1 **Junctional composition of the trophectoderm.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 genes located at cellular junctions with contributory functions as lineage commitment cooperating factors
10 in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

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